

Article

Potential of the Crypto Economy in Financial Management and Fundraising for Tourism

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Abstract: This study aims to examine the potential of blockchain technology in the financing and financial management of entrepreneurial tourism projects. It highlights two objectives: how the technology can be used as an alternative financing tool and how it can improve efficiency and transparency in the financial management of tourism companies. This study shows that initial coin offerings are an effective way to finance innovative tourism projects and that blockchain technology can improve the competitiveness and efficiency of tourism companies. Due to the lack of empirical data on the actual implementation and impact of blockchain technology in the tourism industry, it is suggested that further research is needed to examine the practical application of blockchain technology in the tourism industry, its potential impact on tourism businesses and its implications for the regulatory framework. The proposed methodology includes a systematic literature review on the application of blockchain technology for the financing of tourism projects and the financial improvement of tourism business models. The results indicate that blockchain technology has the potential to transform the financing and financial management of the tourism industry and improve its efficiency and transparency. Furthermore, combining blockchain with other technologies can provide additional benefits in supply chain management and event automation.

Keywords: blockchain; Bitcoin; financing; cryptocurrency; cost efficiency; bibliometric analysis

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1. Introduction

Blockchain technology is defined as an accounting register that has the characteristic of being distributed in a decentralised way using a consensus protocol and a data structure with an architecture resistant to modifications [1]. Since its appearance in 2008 [2], this technology, based on the generation of encrypted blocks of information, has the particularity of being able to store and transmit stored data records containing information about the sender of the transaction, the receiver, the date and time of the transaction, the type of asset transferred and the amount of the same [3]. This type of technology can transfer a type of cryptocurrency to make payments between different countries without having to go through an intermediary, execute a contract between third parties without the need for an intermediary or execute a smart contract [3,4] associated with the automatic resolution of a tourist service reservation contract.

1.1. Blockchain Technology Overview

The growth in the market capitalisation value of cryptocurrencies, which stood at \$1.67 T in January 2022 [5], indicates the level of investment expectations this blockchain technology is generating globally. It is estimated that by 2030, this technology's investments could contribute to a global economic growth of US\$1.76 trillion [6]. Furthermore, this

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